

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Using a Millitome

Using a millitome to cut and register multiple tissue blocks from an organ

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Introduction

Millitomes provide guidance on how to partition an organ, often a complete organ. Millitomes can include either a 3-dimensional (3D) mold that physically holds an organ for partitioning, or a drawing of an organ that is used as a guide by a surgeon when they partition an organ free hand, or both. Using a millitome ensures that tissue sample locations show correctly in the Exploration User Interface.

The 3D millitome (from Latin mille, meaning “thousand,” as in millimeter, and the Greek temnein, meaning “to cut”) is a device designed to hold a freshly procured organ and facilitate cutting it into many small tissue blocks of well defined size for usage in single cell analysis and Human Reference Atlas construction. A millitome has discrete, equally placed cutting grooves in both the x and y directions to guide a carbon steel cutting knife. The millitome is used to produce uniformly sized slices or cubes of tissue material that can be registered to organs from the 3D Reference Object Library. The procedures outlined here describe how to print and use a millitome and how to ensure that spatial locations for each slice or cube are retained for use in atlas construction.

The primary audience for this SOP is the wet bench scientist who will be using a millitome to cut and register multiple tissue blocks from a single organ.

Researchers who wish to understand the procedures used to create millitome templates should consult the SOP on [millitome construction](#) (Kienle et al. 2023). Those interested in how millitomes are fit to reference organs will want to review the SOP titled [Mapping Virtual Millitomes to Reference Organs](#). Roles and responsibilities for those with a part in the procedures are listed in **Table 1**.

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Roles and responsibilities

The **Facilitator** ensures that the process is properly completed. They provide support to the millitome user as needed and work with the HRA Technical Lead to verify that IDs are assigned correctly.

The **Millitome User** secures human organs; downloads millitome data files for relevant organs; 3D prints the millitome; uses it to cut tissue blocks from an organ; and completes and shares the millitome ID lookup table—critical for ensuring that the physical location of each tissue sample is registered within the common coordinate framework used by the Human Reference Atlas.

The **HRA Technical Lead** serves as the liaison to the Infrastructure and Engagement Component (IEC) of the HuBMAP consortium. They deliver the millitome ID lookup table to the IEC and ensure the proper display of the tissue blocks inside the [Exploration User Interface \(EUI\)](#).

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Facilitator	Andreas Bueckle	abueckle@iu.edu
Millitome User	various, based on organ	various
HRA Technical Lead	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@indiana.edu

Procedures

Downloading and printing a millitome

- Visit the HRA millitome website at <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/hra-millitome> to access millitomes for different organs.
- Select the best matching organ(s) in terms of donor sex, organ laterally (if applicable), organ size, and cutting distances, see **Fig. 1**.
- Download a data file package for the customized millitome. The package includes two files:
 - an STL file (Adobe 2023) used to 3D print the millitome tissue cutting tool
 - a CSV lookup file that ties predefined millitome IDs to Sample IDs. This file also contains organ metadata and metadata about the tissue blocks themselves. The CSV lookup file enhances reproducibility by capturing key geometric features of the millitome, such as the scale and block size, and metadata about the organ.
- The file naming schema for all two files is as follows:

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- Format:
[VH]_[gender]_[organ_name]_[block_size_in_mm]_[size_scale]_[laterality]
- Example: VH_F_Kidney_L_10_Medium_Bottom = female kidney, left, 10mm block size, medium (100%), bottom half
- Use a 3D printer to print the file in house or send it to a commercial service for printing.

Figure 1. Left female kidney reference object (left), associated kidney millitome (this is the one for the bottom half of a bisected kidney), and resulting 3D virtual tissue blocks (right).

The CSV lookup file provides the following metadata about the millitome:

Specimen metadata:

- Organ
- Sex
- Laterality (if applicable)
- Size of the tissue block: width, height, depth in mm
- Size of the cutting grid used by the millitome, e.g.: 9x14 blocks and block size in millimeters

Metadata about each millitome ID in the millitome STL:

- x, y, z-position
- x, y-dimension

An exemplary CSV lookup file for the left female kidney VH_F_Kidney_L can be found here:

https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-millitome/blob/main/VH_F_Kidney_L_10_Medium_Bottom.csv

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Using a millitome to cut tissue

Millitome Users are advised to pre-print millitomes of standard sizes and keep them on hand in the lab. This way, they are available when a human organ becomes available so tissue can be cut without delay. 3D printing a millitome takes several hours. The procedures outlined below are general and can be modified to fit your lab's procedures. Maintaining location and orientation of all tissue blocks is key.

- Place the organ in the millitome tray.
- Use a carbon or stainless steel knife to slice the organ, using each of the cutting grooves to place the knife.

It is of utmost importance to keep track of the location and orientation of all tissue blocks. Ice cube trays have been used successfully to keep tissue blocks separated and in order, see **Fig. 2**.

Figure 2. Millitome process for the kidney (from left to right): Digital 3D model of left male kidney, millitome for the lower half of the kidney with 7 x 14 blocks, ice cube tray holding a subset of the tissue blocks, a screenshot showing 98 blocks registered in the EUI.

Completing and submitting the CSV lookup file

The CSV lookup file provided as part of the data package lists millitome IDs that have been pre-assigned to each block in the cutting grid. Millitome IDs are assigned using numbers 1...x for the y-axis, letters a ... z for the x-axis, and letters "b" or "t" for bottom/top laterality. Table 2 shows an example of the CSV lookup file.

Table 2. This table links millitome IDs to sample IDs. Millitome IDs are specific to the reference organ and cutting pattern. Sample IDs are assigned by the research team. Shown here is a blank table for the left female kidney.

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VH_F_Kidney_L_10_Large_Bottom	
Female Kidney left 10x10mm Large Bottom	
Millitome ID	Sample ID
A1	
B1	
C1	
D1	
E1	
F1	
G1	
H1	
A2	
B2	
C2	
D2	
E2	
F2	
G2	
H2	
A3	

- The millitome user records the Sample ID assigned to each tissue sample. This allows data from the tissue sample to be connected to a particular virtual tissue block location within the reference organ. Sample IDs are assigned by the lab team based on their research protocols. Millitome IDs are assigned based on their location in the millitome tray.

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- The millitome user shares the CSV lookup file with the facilitator and the HRA Technical Lead via email.
- The facilitator and the HRA Technical Lead review the table and confirm that the data package is complete.
- The HRA Technical Lead uploads the CSV lookup file to Google Drive at https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1_eUObLbi2_7xJrW2lqMKCmjYtrVBDHF6.
- The HRA Technical Lead shares the CSV lookup file with the IEC. Once the IEC has ingested the millitome data package, the samples become visible in the EUI.

Reviewing millitome tissue registrations

- Once the millitome data package has been ingested by the IEC, the millitome user visits the EUI to verify that the size, placement, and orientation of all tissue blocks is correct. This procedure is outlined in the SOP (Bueckle 2025) describing how to use the Registration User Interface under the section Checking your Registration with the Exploration User Interface.
- If corrections or adjustments are needed, the millitome user contacts the facilitator (email address see Table 1) to make the updates.

References and Resources

Adobe. 2023. "STL Files Explained: Learn about the STL File Format."

<https://www.adobe.com/creativecloud/file-types/image/vector/stl-file.html>.

Bueckle, Andreas. 2025. *SOP: Using the CCF Registration User Interface*. January 16.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14675303>.

Kienle, Peter, Ellen M. Quardokus, and Andreas Bueckle. 2023. *Constructing a Millitome and Generating Virtual Tissue Blocks*. April 15. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7901005>.

Glossary

ASCT+B tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. Tables capture the paratomy of anatomical structures, cell types, and major biomarkers (such as gene, protein, lipid, or metabolic markers). Cellular identity is supported by scientific evidence and linked to ontologies.

lookup table: A tabular mapping of one entity to another, e.g., a phone book (name to number). The millitome lookup table links identification numbers (IDs) in one system (e.g., Millitome IDs) to corresponding identification numbers in another system (HuBMAP IDs).

millitome: Millitomes provide guidance on how to partition an organ, often a complete organ. Millitomes can include either a 3-dimensional mold that physically holds an organ for partitioning, or a drawing of an organ that is used as a guide by a surgeon when they partition

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an organ free hand, or both. Using a millitome ensures that tissue sample locations show correctly in the Exploration User Interface.

sample ID: An ID that uniquely identifies a tissue block, and links it to donor and other metadata. In the HuBMAP consortium, this is referred to as the sample ID.

sterolithography (STL): STL is a file format commonly used for 3D printing and computer-aided design (CAD). STL is also sometimes also referred to as Standard Triangle Language or Standard Tessellation Language. Each file is made up of a series of linked triangles that describe the surface geometry of a 3D model or object. The more complex the design, the more triangles used, and the higher the resolution.

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